

FROM HOME TO HOMELESSNESS: IMPASSE SITUATION OF INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS IN SOUTHERN KADUNA, 1999-2022

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Abstract: The security situation today in the world is as deadly as it is in Nigeria, Kaduna State, and particularly the southern part of Kaduna State. In one of his books, Yusuf Turaki espoused that the area (Southern Kaduna) is inhabited by a group of people known as the Non-Muslim Groups (NMG) and characterised by different ethnic groups numbering over thirty (30) with a distinct culture. The rate of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Southern Kaduna is highly alarming because of the violent attacks perpetrated by insurgency, terrorism farmers/herders clash, and Fulani attacks (unknown gun men). The main aim of this study is to examine the impasse situation faced by IDPs in Southern Kaduna with the following specific objectives: to examine the nature and prevailing conditions in the IDP camps, to ascertain how the IDPs are coping with the condition they found themselves, to assess the impact of the prevailing conditions of the IDPs specifically on the aged, children, and women who are considered to be more vulnerable, to evaluate the impacts of the displacements on the affected communities of Southern Kaduna, and to discuss the response by the state and non-state actors to the challenges that elude the IDPs. The study will help policymakers at all levels understand the impasse situations faced by IDPs in Southern Kaduna as homeless individuals. In carrying out this study, the multi-disciplinary approach will be adopted to enhance and enrich the quality of this study and to provide a platform for cross-examination of ideas to come up with a coherent and acceptable outcome. Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources of information, all of which were objective and subjected to descriptive analysis. The findings show that the IDPs are faced with the challenges of starvation, joblessness, insecurity, lack of food and good drinking water, overcrowding and poor sanitation, hunger, electricity, accommodation shortages, and lack of sustainable occupation, all of which represent serious human security threats for the country.

Keywords: Internally Displaced Persons, Impasse, Situation, Southern Kaduna, Government of Kaduna State.

Introduction

Insecurity in Nigeria has become a threat to the nation, thus making internal displacement a recurring decimal and large-scale phenomenon engulfing virtually every part of the country. The country has experienced many waves of displacement, both on a small and large scale. Post-independence Nigeria had its share of IDPs during the civil war between 1967 and 1970 (Eunice et al., 2023). A good number of eastern Nigerians crossed Nigeria's border to become refugees in neighbouring Cameroon, Chad and Niger, but most southeasterners were internally

displaced within Nigeria. In Nigeria, forced migration and internal displacement in the last 63 years of independence have been triggered by terrorist attacks, violent conflict, natural disasters and environmental degradation, generalised violence, inter-communal and inter-ethnic clashes, land disputes, boundary conflicts between Indigenous people and settlers, communal and ethno-religious clashes, electoral violence and, other forms of human rights violations. It is sad to state that the 21st century is dominated by violence, which is often orchestrated by individuals or groups for certain interests or goals. The violent acts perpetuated are felt by individuals, societies, country(s), and the globe by extension.

According to Kofi Annan, the former Secretary General of the United Nations, internally displaced persons are the most vulnerable of the human family, with displacement seen as ‘the greatest tragedy of our time’ facing the global system and the state (Fenella, 2016). Citizens bear the consequences of insurgency, internal conflicts, and natural disasters and are left to live a life they never bargained for or planned for; hence, they bear the title of Internally Displaced Persons in their land of origin.

Displacement is an occurrence that takes people from their social, educational, economic, and cultural environments and makes them homeless within their country. Internal displacement as a term has always existed, and it became imperative as a concern for global society after the Second World War. The violations of displaced persons’ rights, which mostly arise from intra-state wars around the world, have become dominant after the end of the Cold War (Olanrewaju et al., 2018). Since the end of the Cold War, Africa has witnessed a series of conflicts that have led to millions of displaced persons on the continent. Even though Nigeria, the most populous country in Africa, was not affected by the immediate consequences of the end of the Cold War, the recent upsurge in internal displacement caused by the Boko Haram insurgency and Hausa-Fulani mayhem has resulted in thousands of displacements in Nigeria. The endless surge in internal conflicts is particularly disturbing, with the enormous loss of lives, destruction of public and private infrastructures, and the homeless being a recurring phenomenon in the country (Olanrewaju, Omotoso & Alabi, 2018).

Internal displacement has been increasing in recent years, and the trend continues to increase. In 2014, the former Secretary-General of the United Nations, Ban Ki-Moon, stated in 2014 that displacement remains arguably the most significant humanitarian challenge facing the world. For instance, as of 2014, there were over 30 million internally displaced persons (IDPs) in the world as of 2014, with about one-half of this figure in Sub-Saharan Africa alone, with Nigeria taking the lead (Ejiroghene & Okolie, 2019). As the number of IDPs continues to increase, attempts to manage them become more challenging for these countries.

Between July and October 2012, the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) published a report estimating that 7.7 million people were affected by the flood disaster across the federation. Out of the affected population, 2.1 million people were internally displaced (IDPs); 363 persons died, and 18,282 people were treated for injuries they sustained during the flooding. At the end of 2014, of the 38 million people forcefully displaced by armed conflict and generalised violence globally, Nigeria accounts for at least one million. As of January 2014, approximately 165,000 people were displaced by both floods and conflict in IDP camps in Nigeria. In June 2015, 1,385,298 IDPs were identified in the Northeastern states of Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba, and Yobe stood at 1,385,298 IDPs. As of October 2016, the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), in collaboration with the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), in its 12th round of the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) programme, estimated the total number of IDPs at 2,155,618 across 13 states in Nigeria. As of December 2016, the DTM Round 13 Report estimated 1,770,444 IDPs in the northeast alone (Olanrewaju & Adekunle, 2019).

In Nigeria today, it is unarguably affirmed that the herders are one of the groups that have continued to extensively use arms to negotiate for space and whose activities have perpetually threatened various farmers and communities in Nigeria (Ukasi & Jato, 2020). In the last decade of 2010-2020, the herders have been on a rampage, attacking several communities, particularly in the Middle Belt region, killing farmers and destroying farm produce and farmlands. Little is known about this group because of the clandestine nature of their operations, especially their guerrilla tactics. This approach, adopted by herders in attacking communities, has put many farming communities under perpetual fear (Ukasi & Jato, 2020). Southern Kaduna is one state that has come under severe, endemic attacks from both the herders and terrorists. The attacks have become so severe that virtually all parts of the states have been affected in one way or the other. Thus, it is of interest to note that the terrorists have attacked several communities not only in Southern Kaduna but also elsewhere in the Middle Belt. These attacks have assumed the dimension of a full-scale war of aggression, which has witnessed attackers (terrorists) use sophisticated weapons. Over the years, IDPs in Nigeria, including those in Southern Kaduna, have faced many challenges. These include poor housing in IDP camps, hunger, a gross violation of their rights, and many more impasse situations. Various stakeholders, governments, civil society organisations and regional bodies have tried to address these challenges. Efforts have also been made to address the structural factors that trigger forced displacement. Many of these challenges are borne out of socio-economic, political, and cultural issues, which have increased the rising discontentment and instability in the country, and IDPs are only victims of a broken society where little or no efforts are made by those in charge of affairs of the state to resolve the country's problems.

Statement of the Research Problem

Enwereji (2009), espoused that when violent conflict occurs, internally displaced persons are open to various forms of needs and vulnerability. The most troubling is the shock experienced by these people who are not properly protected by government agencies. This makes their situations even more worrying when weighed alongside the reality that those IDPs are mainly the youth and vulnerable groups (that is, women, children, and the elderly). Existing literature only discusses the challenges of the 'vulnerable groups,' while no considerable attention has been paid to the challenges of displaced men.

Nigeria is bedevilled with security challenges because of the activities of various terrorist groups in the country, which have led to the displacement of thousands of people. Thus, there is no gain in saying that the attacks by different terrorist groups on Southern Kaduna have led to the death of several people while thousands are displaced, causing emotional, psychological, health and other related trauma and social dislocations by those affected by the displacement. In most cases, those affected by these attacks are usually the vulnerable in the community, such as the aged, children, and women. As a result of the impasse situation faced by the IDPs in Nigeria and particularly Southern Kaduna, the federal and state governments, as well as local and international donor organisations, have made concerted efforts to address the plight of the internally displaced people (IDPs) within the confines of the resources at their disposal through a variety of measures, such as the provision of food and non-food items (DTM, 2020). It is against the backdrop of these situations faced by the IDPs in Southern Kaduna that this study seeks to interrogate the impasse situation of IDPs in Southern Kaduna, who suddenly, became homeless as a result of terror attacks on their communities and were compelled to live in unfavourable conditions.

This study will answer the following research questions:

- a. What is the nature of the IDP camps and the prevailing?
- b. How have the IDPs coped with the conditions in which they found themselves?

- c. What is the impact of the prevailing conditions of the IDPs, specifically on the vulnerable aged, children, and women?
- d. What are the impacts of the displacements on the affected communities in Southern Kaduna?
- e. What are the responses of state and non-state actors to the challenges that elude IDPs in Southern Kaduna?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine the situation of IDPs in Southern Kaduna. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- a. To examine the nature and prevailing conditions in IDP camps.
- b. To ascertain how IDPs cope with the conditions they find themselves in.
- c. To assess the impact of the prevailing conditions of IDPs, specifically on the aged, children, and women who are considered vulnerable.
- d. To evaluate the impacts of displacement on the affected communities of Southern Kaduna.
- e. To discuss the responses of state and non-state actors to the challenges that elude IDPs.

Scope of the Study

The study seeks to discuss the impasse situation of IDPs in Southern Kaduna from 1999 to 2022. 1999 is considered the starting point to mark the return of democracy (fourth republic) after a long period of military rule in Nigeria. This period is also important because it ushered in several violent activities, ranging from Boko Haram insurgency, banditry, farmers-herders clashes, kidnapping, Fulani attacks on different communities, and many other violent activities experienced with the return of democracy in Nigeria. Similarly, 2023 is taken as the terminal point to coincide with Nigeria's last general elections. This period was chosen to enable researchers to look into the impasse situations of the IDPs in Southern Kaduna and the government's role in alleviating the IDPs' challenges. This will help the researchers in assessing the period of the research before the newly elected leadership of 2023, which had individuals or groups find refuge in a temporary place, thereby making them internally displaced.

The study was conducted in the Southern Kaduna area of Kaduna State, which is made up of eight (8) local government areas (Jaba, Jema'a, Kachia, Kagarko, Kaura, Kuru, Sanga, and Zangon-Kataf). The timeframe for this study was chosen because the area is more broadly representative of the diverse groups of persons from the North Central who have been adversely affected as a result of terrorism. However, the government of Nigeria, which signed the Kampala Convention agreement in 2009, has not done much in assisting displaced persons in Nigeria generally and particularly in Southern Kaduna, which informs the reason for this study's time frame.

Significance of the Study

Several studies or publications exist on IDPs globally and, by extension, the Nigerian state, but they are not anchored on the situations of the IDPs in Southern Kaduna, Kaduna state. Therefore, this research is imperative because it is going to fill a gap in knowledge and create awareness of the impasse situations of displaced persons in Southern Kaduna and how the state, through its mechanisms, has catered for the needs of the IDPs.

This work is beneficial to future research students who would want to carry out further studies on IDPs, which will enable the government to gain more insights on the challenges of IDPs in Nigeria, and also help them (the government) make and implement policies to mitigate the plights of displaced men in Nigeria, and further create ways to resolve or improve the situations faced by the IDPs.

Conceptual Clarification

Given the nature of this research work, it is pertinent to clarify some keywords adopted in the study, which will be IDPs and Southern Kaduna.

Internally Displaced Persons

Internally displaced persons are individuals or groups of people who are displaced within a geographical location. Because of the displacement, they suffer several consequences or hardships, thereby denying them their livelihood.

According to the United Nations, under international law, IDPs are those people or individuals who were forced to leave their place or homes as a consequence of or to avoid the outcome of armed struggle, occasions of widespread hostility, man-made disaster, or human rights violations, and have remained within their country's boundary as displaced persons (Akuto, 2017). In Akuto's (2017) view, IDPs are people who were displaced by conflict or natural disaster from their habitual residence and have not gone beyond a country's national borders. Mohammed (2017) argued that IDPs, unlike refugees, are those who did not cross an international border but remained within the borders of their country.

A pictorial of people in IDP camps in various parts of Southern Kaduna is attached.

Source: Layfaithful Trust Foundation, 2023

Southern Kaduna

The history of Southern Kaduna is a Pandora’s box of domination struggles. It is full of intrigues and conspiracies, laying claim to ownership of land and other natural resources, indigene-ship and socio-political rights, as well as traditional leadership rights, which has given birth to potential conflict between Hausa-Fulani Muslims and indigenous Christians.

Source: Ministry of Health of Kaduna State, 2022

The term “Southern Kaduna” has been controversially used for decades. Some authors suggest that it first came into usage to refer to the southern part of Kaduna State (which officially came into being in 1987). On the other hand, other scholars insist that the term came into official parlance after 1907, which refers to the districts belonging to the Southern Division of Zaria Province, which was established by the British colonial administration. The decision for this administrative change was a result of the confederation of Christian ethnic nationalities’ persistent revolt against Muslim-controlled Zaria, especially from 1901 onwards when British colonial forces conquered the territory (Abdulbarkindo et al., 2018).

Geographically, the latitude of the territory of Southern Kaduna lies between 70°N and 100°N and the longitude between 50°E and 70°E. The territory contains a potpourri of over 30 ethnic nationalities, including: Atyap, Attachirak, Tsam, Kagoma, Fantswam, Adara, Akurmi, Ninkyop, Ninzo, Ham, Mada, Asholio, and others, all of whom are predominantly Christian. According to Joseph Greenberg’s classification of African languages, most ethnic nationalities in Southern Kaduna belong to the Platoid group of languages (Abdulbarkindo et al., 2018).

Review of Related Literature

Over the years, scholars have made significant efforts to bring a definite definition of IDPs to the fore. However, a more popular definition of IDP by Goodwin-Gill (2007) sees an IDP as someone who has moved within the bounds of his or her own country either to escape persecution, other violation of human rights, or the effects of conflict or because of a national or development project, such as high-dam building. According to the United Nations Human Rights (2019), persons forced to flee or leave their homes are generally subject to heightened vulnerability in member areas, particularly in situations of armed conflict. Displaced persons suffer significantly higher mortality rates than the general population. They also remain at high risk of a physical attack. Sexual assault and abduction, and they are frequently deprived of adequate shelter, food, and health services.

Olanrewaju and Adekunle (2019) examined insurgency and the invisible displaced population in Nigeria. The study addressed the gap in the effects of the invisibility of IDPs living in host communities to the government, as less attention has been given to the discriminatory treatment of IDPs in host communities arising from the government’s neglect of providing humanitarian aid to IDPs in host communities, despite the government’s presence in formal camps. The study deployed Vulnerability Theory as its theoretical compass and employed interviews and FGDs as its research instruments. The study found that the destinations of IDP settlements were very vulnerable in terms of their access to quality education, shelter, food, health care, and potable water, as they were often cut off from the government’s humanitarian interventions and only visible to NGOs and individual philanthropists who have limited resources to allocate. The study recommended, among others, the establishment of a holistic intervention mechanism in managing the displacement crisis in Nigeria, irrespective of the resettlement destination.

Oduwole and Fadeyi (2013) evaluated the state of IDPs in Nigeria. The study elicited information using an ethnographic approach; a semi-structured interview was purposefully conducted on some of the survivors of the bomb attack on the UN building in Abuja. The major findings of the study revealed that the state apparatus (government) neglected to ensure better, more effective, and functional policies. Its magnitude is capable of threatening the country’s national cohesion and endangering a high rate of IDPs across the country. The study concluded that given the magnitude and complexity of internal displacement crises, they are inimical to the discourse “Development”. This prevents the country from achieving Millennium Development Goal number eight (8): rights to the safety of lives and properties as equally enshrined in other international treaties, choices to a

healthy, creative life, and to enjoy a decent standard of living, freedom, dignity, self-respect, and the respect of others.

According to Titilope et al. (2019), the Boko Haram insurgency has led to major displacement, particularly in Nigeria's northeastern region. The study used a qualitative approach and thematic analysis to explain the major problems of integration among women with IDF. The study identified the struggle to return home, security concerns, poor infrastructure, and lack of economic opportunities as the major challenges affecting the integration of displaced women. The government and other stakeholders were recommended to adopt the Inter-Agency Standing Committee framework to address the integration of IDW in Nigeria.

Olanrewaju et al. (2018) examined the challenges facing IDPs to evaluate the effects of humanitarian response projects in alleviating these challenges. This study deployed a mixed-methods approach in data collection and analysis with quantitative dominance. The study identified hunger, lack of clothing, regular sickness, and lack of drugs as the major challenges confronting IDPs. The study also found that humanitarian services positively impacted the IDPs, yet the government and the humanitarian services providers need to put more effort into alleviating the suffering of the IDPs in Nigeria.

Eunice et al. (2023) disclosed that the challenges facing displaced people in Nigeria as a result of Boko Haram, natural and man-made disasters, as well as the Hausa-Fulani Mayhem, are peculiar to all the IDPs irrespective of demographic disparities. This study employed qualitative and quantitative research methods, drawing data from primary and secondary sources. The questionnaire was administered to 256 respondents and complemented by KII and FGDs with IDPs in the study area. The study found that starvation, inadequate potable water supply, hunger, lack of electricity, accommodation shortages, and lack of sustainable occupation foretell serious human security threats for the country. The study recommended relevant policies for the government and other related agencies working with the IDPs, while concluding that the government should collaborate with individuals and organisations in providing vocational skills, which will help alleviate their plights.

Theoretical Framework

To give this research work a solid foundation, the human theory is adopted. The theory is appropriate for this research as it gives a broader insight into the IDPs' impasse situation in Southern Kaduna and helps, to reflect an overall justification of the study.

Human Needs Theory

This research work is anchored on the human needs theory proposed by Abraham Maslow in his work "A Theory of Human Motivation" in Psychological Review in 1943. The theory asserts that human needs are universal and not negotiable. It further states that some needs are more significant for the well-being of human survival. The theory further posits that the reason for conflict is the underlying needs of persons to meet their needs as individuals, as a society, and at the group level. According to Danielson (2005), the human needs theory is important in providing insight into the causes and resolution of conflict. Danielson further sees the human needs theory as an instrument for mediation, preventive peace building, and post-conflict peace building. Similarly, the relationship between conflict and human needs rests on the premise that conflict occurs when the needs of individuals and groups are not met (Olanrewaju, Omotoso & Alabi, 2018). Therefore, it is pertinent to state that conflict resolution would be more effective when all varying interests are addressed and human needs are met. It is therefore the duty of the government in every society to make decisions and policies that are aimed at solving social problems that could negatively affect the lives of the people. Hence, the government has the responsibility to initiate policies that are geared towards solving social problems. Institutions such as NEMA/SEMA were

created to cushion the situations faced by IDPs in Nigeria to cater for the needs of displaced persons, which have little or no positive impacts/results on the IDPs. This is because they (the IDPs) lack what Maslow calls pressing needs, such as water, food, and shelter.

Research Methodology

The study adopted the survey research method, which is flexible and allows for various methods to be employed in conducting the research. Hence, both quantitative and qualitative research approaches were adopted. Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources of information, all of which were objective and subjected to descriptive analysis.

- A. **Research Design:** A research design is the procedure for the collection, analysis, interpretation and reporting data in a research work. Although there are several other research designs, the explanatory research design was adopted for this work to enable an understanding of the IDPs' impasse situations in Southern Kaduna. Oral interviews were conducted among the different communities inhabiting the study area. The oral interview will be categorised into two groups, and individual interviews. Open-ended questionnaires will be administered. Secondary sources were also utilised, and published books contributed by other scholars on the subject matter were consulted. These works were useful in understanding some challenges that were perhaps not properly understood from the oral sources. Unpublished works, such as thesis, seminar papers, and conference papers, will also constitute useful source material for this research work.
- B. **Population:** This study's population comprises IDPs, farmers, government officials, politicians, security personnel, and traditional rulers.
- C. **Sample Technique:** Stratified sampling was used for objectivity. Four groups were identified: IDPs, farmers (community residents), government officials (civil servants, local politicians, security personnel), and traditional rulers. Having stratified these groups, a total of 300 respondents out of 120 persons from the IDP camps are dependents, 100 farmers, 60 civil servants from the affected communities, and 20 traditional rulers will be randomly administered questionnaires, making a total of 300 respondents, while others will be interviewed.
- D. **Method of Data Collection:** The researcher(s) visited communities that were forced into homelessness to collect and gather data from the field alongside the assistants. The researcher(s) and the assistants monitored the filling of the questionnaires in person. Research assistants were used in places where the researchers had difficulties that might be caused by language or religious barriers, difficulty in assessing certain areas in the communities, or perhaps traditional barriers. Considerable attention was given to the cross-examination of the responses.
- E. **Method of Data Analysis:** This study employed a qualitative data analysis method. This section provides descriptive information, explanations, and interpretation of interview transcripts and surveys.
- F. **Study Area:** The study area (Southern Kaduna) is made up of eight (8) local government areas (LGAs), which include: Jaba, Jema'a, Kaura, Kauru, Sanga, Zango-Kataf, Kachia, and Kagarko. The area is related to various ethnic groups the Middle Belt region of Nigeria. James (2007) classified the people based on their ethnolinguistic affinities under the topic, 'The Middle Belt: Composition of the Nok Culture Area'.

Data presentation and analysis

Presentation of the Data

Table 1.1: Response Frequency

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Options	Frequency	Percentage
Valid	300	100%
Unfilled	Nil	0%
Total	300	100%

Table 1 shows the responses of the respondents after the researcher administered the questionnaire. A total of 300 questionnaires were administered, out of the 300 questionnaires administered, none of the questionnaires were invalid or mutilated; rather, it was all answered, thereby making the 300 questionnaires valid and functional for this research, which was 100% of the allotted questionnaires.

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 1.2: Features of the Respondents

Demographic information	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	90	30%
Female	210	70%
Age		
1-15	80	26.7%
16-30	85	28.3%
31-45	75	25%
46+	60	20%
Marital Status		
Single	104	34.7%
Married	106	35.3%
Separated	37	12.3%
Widowed	53	17.7%
Education Level		
No Qualification	33	11%
Primary Certificate	57	19%
WAEC	92	30.7%
BS.C	78	26%
MS.C	23	7.7%
MBA	17	5.6%
Total	300	100%

The table above shows that 30% of the respondents were men and 70% were women. Of the respondents, 26.7% were ages 1–15, 16–30 were 28.3%, 25% were 31–45, and 20% were 46 and above. 34.7% are single, 35.3% are married, 12.3% are separated, and 17.7% are widowed. Regarding educational qualification, 11% did not attend formal education, 19% had a primary certificate, 30.7% had WAEC, 26% had BS.C, 7.7% had M.Sc, and 5.6% had MBA. It is necessary to state that a good number of displaced persons had acquired formal education.

Stratification of the respondents

Table 1.3: Social Status of the Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Dependents	120	40%
Local Farmers	100	33.3%
Civil Servants	60	20%
Traditional Rulers	20	6.7%
Total	300	100

The table above shows that 40% of the respondents were dependents, 33.3% were local farmers, 20% were civil servants, and 6.7% were traditional rulers. This, by implication, shows that the IDPs were able to cut across all statuses of life.

Respondent Question 1

Table 1.4: Are the Conditions in the IDP Camps Conducive?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	0	0%
No	293	97.7%
Undecided	7	2.3%
Total	300	100%

The table above indicates that 0% of the respondents were silent about the conditions at the camp, 97.7% agreed that the conditions at the IDP camps were not conducive, and 2.3% did not know if the conditions were conducive or not. Therefore, the respondents submitted that the conditions faced at the IDP camp were not conducive.

Respondent Question 2

Table 1.5: Are the IDPS Coping with the Condition in which they Found Themselves?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	30	10%
No	217	72.3%
Undecided	53	17.7%
Total	300	100%

The above table shows that 10% of the respondents said they were coping with the condition they found themselves in, while 72.3% were not coping with the conditions at the IDP camps, and 17.7% were undecided. Therefore, it is important to state that based on the responses of the respondents, the camp was not favourable; thus, they find it difficult to cope with the condition.

Respondent Question 3

Table 1.6: Does the Prevailing Conditions of IDPs Specifically Affect the Aged, Children and Women Considered Vulnerable?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	261	87%
No	23	7.3%
Undecided	16	5.3%
Total	300	100%

The table above shows that 87% of the respondents agreed that the condition at the IDP camp, specifically on the aged, children, and women, should be considered vulnerable, 7.3% did not agree, and 5.3% were undecided. This, by implication, shows that the elderly, children, and women are vulnerable.

Respondent Question 4

Table 1.7: Impacts of Displacements on the Affected Communities of Southern Kaduna?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	271	90.3%
No	18	6%
Undecided	11	3.7%
Total	300	100%

The table above indicates that 90.3% of the respondents said displacements have impacts on the affected communities, 6% agreed that there are no impacts, and 2.3% were undecided. Therefore, it is the submission of the respondents that the displacement has impacts on the affected communities.

Respondent Question 5

Table 1.8: Does the State and Non-State Actors Respond to the Challenges that Elude IDPs in Southern Kaduna?

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	90	30%
No	187	62.3%
Undecided	23	7.6%
Total	300	100%

The above table shows that 30% of the respondents said there was a response from both state and non-state actors to the IDP camp in Southern Kaduna, while 62.3% said there was no response from either the state or non-state actors to the IDP camp in Southern Kaduna, and 7.6% were undecided. Therefore, it is important to state that the responses of the respondents shows that there was no response from either the state or non-state actors to the IDPs’ challenges in Southern Kaduna.

Summary and Recommendations

This study attempts to bridge an existing gap in the literature on the challenges faced by displaced persons in Southern Kaduna. This shows that IDPs in the area under study face various problems, such as a lack of good drinking water, food, shelter, unemployment, insecurity, and other salient issues. Although most respondents disagreed that the government has been committed to protecting and providing for their needs, the Nigerian government is encouraged to look into the plights of the IDPs in the area (Southern Kaduna). Most of the respondents indicated that the major challenge they face in reintegrating back into society is the issue of insecurity perpetuated by their attackers who claimed to be unknown gunmen. Hence, a government whose sole responsibility is to protect its citizens must ensure that the safety of IDPs is ensured within its territorial boundary. Based on the findings of this study, the study recommends the following:

1. The government should adopt the UN Guiding Principles and the Kampala Convention on Internal Displacement Persons.
2. The government should incorporate national policy into domestic laws to help improve the situation of IDPs.
3. The government should ensure that it puts all mechanisms in place to protect and provide for the needs of IDPs, as well as security to enable them to reintegrate and resettle with their families in the society where they were domiciled before displacement occurred.
4. Officers saddled with the responsibility of caring for displaced persons should be checked regularly to avoid corruption.
5. A deliberate attempt by the government should be made to create vocational training programmes for IDPs, which will go a long way in solving the challenges of unemployment faced by them (IDPs).
6. Counselling sections should also be organise by government agencies responsible for taking care of IDPs to help them deal with the trauma they face as displaced persons.

Conclusion

It is the submission of this paper that the IDPs in Southern Kaduna are indeed faced with an impasse situation and thus became, displaced, finding refuge in a totally different environment, thereby becoming homeless (from

home to homelessness). The Nigerian government should work with the appropriate authorities to prevent and curb some of the challenges the IDPs face, which include: overcrowded accommodation, littered environment, water shortages, and food and medical facilities, which have caused outbreaks of diseases, thereby exposing the IDPs to avoidable health risks. If this is done, it will definitely go a long way in mitigating the plights of the IDPs in Southern Kaduna and, by extension, Nigeria at large.

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